

Classification of fine arts according to Kant

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Abstract. In this study, I create a classification of the fine arts according to Kant, based on his analysis of the sublime in the Critique of Judgment.

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1. Introduction

Example. Fine Art¹

In the work "Critique of Judgment", Kant conducts an analysis of the sublime. In it, Kant devotes text² to the classification and difference between the refined arts. In this article, I briefly outline the classification of the refined arts by characteristics using tables, trying to make them as informative as possible.

2. Main part

Kant groups sculpture and architecture under "Plastic Arts", but since they have some different characteristics that can be classified, I do not group them under one category.

name of fine art/characteristic	Verbal Arts	Visual Arts	Art of the Play of Sensations
Oratory	+	-	-
Poetic art	+	-	-
sculpture	-	+	-
architecture	-	+	-
Painting	-	+	-
Music	-	-	+
Art of colors	-	-	+

Part 1

name of fine art/characteristic	Freedom and Play of Imagination	Connection with Moral Ideas	Mathematical Proportion and Form	Cultural and Cognitive Development
Oratory	-	-	-	-
Poetic art	+	+	-	+
sculpture	-	-	-	+
architecture	-	-	+	-
Painting	-	+	-	+
Music	+	-	+	-
Art of colors	-	-	-	-

Part 2

name of fine art/characteristic	Transient (Short-Term) Impact	Lasting (Long-Term) Impact	Social Applicability and Influence
Oratory	-	-	-
Poetic art	-	+	-
sculpture	-	+	-
architecture	-	-	-
Painting	-	-	+
Music	+	-	+
Art of colors	+	-	-

Part 3

The 3 parts of the table provide a brief but informative overview of Kant's understanding of the fine arts.

3. Conclusion

In this study, I created a classification of the fine arts according to Kant, based on his analysis of the sublime in the Critique of Judgment.

References

1. [What Is Fine Art? Definition & Examples](#). Robert Lange Studios (en.).
2. Кант, Імануель (2022). Критика сили судження (укр) . Київ: Темпора. с. 218-232. ISBN 978-617-569-541-8.